

ELECTRODES AGED UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELDS EMITTED BY TECTONIC STRESS

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The work is based on the assumption that an electrochemical cell, under the influence of electromagnetic fields emitted by the Earth's crust in conditions of tectonic stress, will function as an electrical pile on account of potential electrode differences. The signal obtained can be correlated in the long term with energy sources that derive from the activity of the Sun, from the relative position of the Sun, Earth and Moon, or from the nearby and very distance tectonic processes, the identification of electric/electromagnetic precursors of significant earthquakes, becoming possible.

Studies on the behavior of electrodes over long intervals (1.5 - 2 years) have highlighted an increase in the potential difference of polarization between two identical electrodes, but with reduced changes in electrode noise (Petiau and Dupis, 1980). Karpen oxygen cells (electrodes of Au and platinated Au, in concentrated sulphuric acid), or those with hydrogen (platinated Pt and Au, in diluted sulphuric acid) bring into question the fact that long-time operation (15 and 68 years) is due to thermal flux established between the exterior and the interior of the pile, due to the endothermic processes in the electrochemical system (Vaszilcsin et al., 2016). Miyacoshi (1986) shows that older electrodes can be sensitive to the SP variations of a fractured area belonging to an active fault, and can be highlighted electric precursors of earthquakes.

The evolution over time of electrochemical corrosion is estimated by calculating, based on experimental data and empirical relationships, the double-logarithmic diagrams on weight loss and the corrosion rate of the sample on 1-4-year durations, which then allow extrapolations of up to 40 years (Badea et al., 2002, Haghymas et al., 1963).

The constructive variant chosen by us to obtain long-term differences of electrode potential (15 years), consisted in the realization of a double electric pile, in which the three electrodes are brass cylinders, of centimetric size (Fig. No. 1), with equal masses and surfaces, but of different shapes, immersed in seven liters of NaCl solution, stationary (Furnica, 2016a).

The external circuit, of electronic conduction, consisting of a ULF active filter (< 40 Hz) and a millivoltmeter, was different, depending on the conditions and location of the site, having impedance of about 1M Ω . Between the start working (26.11.2001) and the definitive stop (12.10.2016), the recordings on paper and then only by noting the values ΔV read on the scale of an analogue millivoltmeter, were performed in the following stages: 1) 26.11.2001-4.07.2005, location in observatory conditions, in the basement of a building of Institutes of Geodynamics, in Bucharest, ULF filter and recorder on paper (Servo 150); 2) 4.07.2005-31.01.2006, without the recorder, but with the filter in function; 3) 31.01.2006-27.07.2006, with filter and analogue millivoltmeter, on the one floor of another building in the immediate vicinity, in conditions that led to drying of the electrolyte solution after no more than 2 years.

The appearance of aged electrode was evident at the end of the observations, with the opening the lid of the vat on which the brass cylinders were fixed in the working position. After a period of about 6 years of full immersion, followed by about 2 years in which the electrolyte solution evaporated, 8 years in which the electric potential differences were obtained further from an electrochemical system in which internal resistance would be had to be close to that of the air in the work room, the notion of electrode has become out of the definition.

Fig. 1 Brass cylinders consisting of double-pile electrodes "SLD_2": L (anode), N (common electrode), R (cathode)

It was found that the deposits of salts on the vat's walls respect a certain polarity inside. Those from the west and the north magnetic of the location are almost deprived of the crusts, while those from the east and the south magnetic, are well covered with specific structures of sodium chloride, deposited by evaporation.

In long time, brass (copper alloyed with zinc) supports important corrosion phenomena if it is in alkaline solutions (0.050 mm/year), in sodium chloride solutions (0.207 mm/year), in seawater (0.050 mm/year), or due to the action of microorganisms (Haghyamas et al., 1963, Badea et al., 2002). Observing the appearance of the cylinders used in the SLD_2 transducer for 15 years, are distinguished helical structures elongated vertically, especially on the central electrode (the null), less on the cathode (R) and very little on the anode (L) (Fig. No. 2 and 3).

The resemblance to the structures called *rusticles*, discovered on the Titanic wreck located at the bottom of the Atlantic Ocean, at pressures and temperatures specific to the depth of 4000 m, led us to the assumption that the deposits of corrosion products on the cylinders of brass from the vat with NaCl solution, should be with Cu_2O , CuO , $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, or NaCl (Haghyamas et al. 1963). However, the form of helical and stalactite-like development seems closer to the speleothem *helictites* which is found in cave conditions, at lower pressures and temperatures higher than the rusticles on the ocean floor. Both appear in areas with content rich in metals, such as Fe from the metal components of the wreckage, or Mn, Fe, Cu, on limited areas of caves located in areas of fault, or near thermal anomalies. It is known that their growth is due to some communities of microorganisms, which utilize these metals, resulting in complex mineral structures, rich in calcite and aragonite (Cullimore et al., 2002, Palmer, 2017, Tisato et al., 2015).

The fact that many types of helictites does not present the central channel, specific to an activity of organic nature, has led to the proposal for other possibilities of forming and

growth, especially if it is taken into account the changes in direction during the growth, which sometimes there have nothing common with the direction of gravity: capillary forces, wind, piezoelectric forces (Wikipedia, 2019).

In all situations encountered in the literature it is surprisingly that, in the conditions of large electrical conductivity specific to salt solutions, are invoked electrical currents given by the electrolyte activity of different metals belonging to wreckage in seawater, and in the fault zones of caves by piezoelectricity phenomena, because of the tectonic activity. Therefore, we consider that in situations where the electrodes were placed during the 15 years, the electric currents of double-pile, whose variations depended on electromagnetic fields of external tectonic stress, influenced the corrosion processes on the cylinders of brass, the rate of growth in the form of helictites being much superior to that considered in natural conditions: approximately 3.2 cm on the central electrode, 1.7 cm on the cathode (R) and 1.6 cm on the anode (L), comparatively with a few centimeters in 100 years, in caves.

Fig. 2 Electrodes L, N and R, after 15 years of operation, and corrosion deposits in the form of helictites

Fig. 3 Detail on the growth spiral right-hand twisted, considered to be a helictite obtained in laboratory conditions

In the same category, of the importance of natural electrical currents, we should consider our observation that, in 5 out of 5 cases, the caves with helictites are close to the tectonic vortices of regional extension, evidenced by geomorphological appearance, on satellite topographic maps, in North America, Australia and Europe. The novelty can have a special value in investigating in this regard the tectonic vortex of the Apuseni Mountains, in Romania, also identified on geomorphological considerations (Furnica, 2016b).

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